

Script and Study Flow

Step 0: Set up

Before participants arrive, make sure you have the following things checked:

- The Wifi connection is working in the study room
- There are at least 25 seats in each room (B209 and room C209 (Tervahovi))
- Check which room is more appropriate for independent work with Ciperbot and which room is more suitable for watching a video with a deepfake. Based on the appropriateness, arrange the tables and chairs accordingly in these two rooms
- There is at least 1 screen in each room which are for slides
- The 50 copies of the consent form are printed. Moderator 1 has the consent forms printed out and Moderator 1 will bring the consent forms to the study session.
- Each consent form has the unique ParticipantID (running number from P01-P60)

Step 1: Welcome (Introduction + Consent form)

08.30

All moderators go first to room B209. Before participants enter the room, one of the moderators opens the presentation on the screen of the room for the participants to later observe.

09:00-09:15 Introduction

Moderator 1 and other moderators (Moderator 3, Moderator 2, Moderator 4 and Moderator 5) are welcoming participants in the room. When participants are seated, Moderator 1 introduces the team of moderators and shares the agenda of the user study to the participants, following the slides in the presentation (already on the screen). All slides in the presentation follow this script and contain tips of what is going on now and next during the user study session. Moreover, all slides are marked with a timeline in the upper right corner which helps moderators to follow the schedule.

09:15 - 09:25 Consent form

After the introduction, the printed consent forms are distributed among the participants. The moderators assist in distributing the consent forms and blank paper sheets for personal notes. The moderators answer any questions the participants may have. The moderators emphasize to the participants to keep the consent form until the study session is over. The moderators give the participants 10 minutes to read and sign it.

09:25 - 09:35 Pre-survey

One of the moderators selects slide number 6 in the slide deck on the screen. There is a link for the pre-survey on slide 6. Participants are instructed to open their own computers, type a hyperlink for the survey, and answer the questions in the pre-survey.

09:35 - 09:50 Dividing the participants into 2 groups

Moderator 1 gives an explanation of the experiment to the participants, saying: “In this user study, you will be randomly divided into two groups. One group will receive an explanation of Data-driven Persona, while the other group will learn about Data-driven Persona independently. Please bear in mind that you will be given a work task scenario, asked to answer post-survey questions, and to provide feedback on the experiment.”

After that Moderator 1 reads the Work Task Scenario:

“Explain how development could be used to create student personas for a marketing course that you are teaching (or you have participated in as a student). Be as specific as you can.

- data collection (what data to collect, how, and how much),
- data analysis (how to segment the data),
- persona building (how to create persona profiles from the segments),
- and evaluation (how to evaluate that the personas are accurate and useful).”

The last part of this pre-survey section involves dividing participants into two groups. All participants with even ID numbers on their consent forms are instructed to follow one of the moderators and go to room C209, where the participants will use Chiperbot¹. The other group remains in Room B209.

Step 2: The experiment

09:50 - 10:20 Learn about

In the next half hour participants will be under the experiment. Moderators will be splitted into 2 rooms too in order to control the process.

Room B209 - video explanation

Moderator 1, Doctoral Student

Moderator 5, Associate Professor

¹ <https://cipherbot.qcri.org/signin>

Moderator 1 gives instructions to the participants that they will now watch a 10-minute video and are welcome to take notes. Moderator 1 clarifies that no questions will be answered by the moderators, as all the necessary information is provided within the video.

Moderator 1 makes sure that every participant is able to hear the audio and see the screen well and after that Moderator 1 switches on the deepfake video on the screen.

Room C209 - chatbot explanation

Moderator 2, Doctoral Student

Moderator 3, Doctoral Student

Moderator 2 is responsible for managing the screen in room C209.

Moderator 2 will explain to the participants that there are three modes of interaction with the bot. The participants will receive a brief training session on how to use CIPHERBOT, presented in the slides, titled “5 Tips for Using CIPHERBOT.” Moderator 2 will lead this training.

Participants will use the “Learn” mode, and the slides will also provide guidance on the Work Task Scenario points the participants need to cover while interacting with the chatbot. Participants will have 5 minutes to log in. Moderators will check that everyone has successfully logged in and that there are no issues. After that, participants will have 10 minutes to use the chatbot. Moderator 2 will ensure that all time limits are followed.

10:20 - 10:50 Post-survey + Learning task

There are two different post-surveys for two rooms.

Room B209 - video explanation

When the participants have watched the video, Moderator 1 asks the participants to type the hyperlink displayed on the presentation slides and fill in the post-survey.

Room C209 - chatbot explanation

When time (10 minutes of the interaction with the chatbot) is out, a moderator 2 asks to type the hyperlink displayed on the presentation slides and fill in the post-survey. After that, participants are informed that the experiment has ended and that they may leave the premises. Moderators then collect the consent forms and any personal notes from the participants.